

Cultivar	DAPE ^a	High density grains/ panicle		Good grains/ panicle		Av grains/ panicle		Poor grains/ panicle		Unfilled grains/ panicle		Total grains/ panicle (no.)
		no.	% ^b	no.	%	no.	%	no.	%	no.	%	
Pusa 2-21	15	83	(55.2)	2	(1.3)	4	(2.7)	10	(6.9)	51	(33.9)	150
	20	105	(59.3)	4	(2.3)	4	(2.7)	32	(18.2)	32	(18.1)	177
	25	94	(59.9)	16	(10.2)	12	(7.6)	26	(16.6)	9	(5.8)	157
	30	73	(50.0)	13	(8.9)	11	(7.5)	35	(24.0)	14	(9.6)	146
	35	81	(51.3)	30	(19.0)	15	(9.5)	25	(15.8)	7	(4.4)	158
Pusa 743	15	0.3	(0.2)	15	(8.8)	35	(20.6)	48	(28.2)	72	(42.3)	170
	20	14	(9.2)	78	(51.3)	7	(4.6)	24	(15.8)	29	(19.1)	152
	25	2	(1.3)	74	(47.1)	38	(24.2)	18	(11.5)	25	(15.9)	157
	30	2	(1.4)	72	(50.7)	3	(19.1)	9	(6.3)	32	(22.5)	142
	35	13	(10.0)	59	(45.7)	17	(13.2)	15	(11.6)	25	(19.4)	129
Pusa 169	15	0.3	(0.2)	19	(10.3)	32	(17.4)	40	(21.7)	93	(50.5)	184
	20	2	(1.2)	50	(30.7)	12	(7.4)	15	(9.2)	84	(51.5)	163
	25	1	(0.5)	27	(14.4)	46	(24.5)	27	(14.4)	87	(46.3)	188
	30	1	(0.7)	25	(17.6)	45	(31.7)	25	(17.6)	46	(32.4)	142
	35	7	(3.6)	50	(25.4)	30	(15.2)	46	(23.4)	64	(32.5)	197
Jaya	15	12	(7.2)	65	(39.2)	22	(13.3)	18	(10.8)	49	(29.5)	166
	20	16	(8.7)	73	(39.4)	27	(14.8)	21	(11.5)	46	(25.1)	183
	25	34	(17.7)	85	(44.3)	16	(8.3)	27	(14.0)	30	(15.6)	192
	30	33	(18.6)	82	(46.3)	17	(9.6)	33	(18.6)	12	(6.8)	177
	35	41	(22.0)	76	(40.9)	16	(8.6)	33	(17.7)	20	(10.8)	186

^aDAPE = d after panicle emergence. ^bNumbers in parentheses indicate percentage of total grains/panicle.

Pest resistance—diseases

Using pedigree analysis to identify sources of resistance to rice hoja blanca virus (RHBV)

F. Cuevas-Pérez, Apartado Aéreo 67-13, Cali, Colombia; C. Ventura-Flores, Universidad Nacional Pedro Ruiz Gallo, Chiclayo, Peru; and F. Correa-Victoria, International Center for Tropical Agriculture (CIAT) Rice Program, Cali, Colombia

RHBV is the only virus disease of rice in the western hemisphere. It is restricted to Latin America. The insect *Tagosodes orizicolus* (Muir) transmits RHBV. To identify the original sources of resistance, we searched the literature for varieties and lines reported as resistant or moderately resistant to RHBV and conducted pedigree analyses.

Cultivars reported to have some degree of resistance, their parents with unknown reaction, and some landraces contributing to the pedigrees were evaluated in the greenhouse for their

reaction to RHBV. Cages (2 × 1 × 1 m) with capacity for 180 pots, each containing 10 plants, were used. Ten pots with 15-d-old plants of each genotype were randomly distributed within the cage and exposed for 5 d to a colony of the insect vector with at least 70% of the individuals carrying the virus. Each plant was assessed for disease symptoms 15 d after exposure.

Eight of the nine varieties or lines previously reported as resistant to RHBV showed infections of less than 30%, which is the accepted resistance level (see table). The susceptible reaction of line IR1721-146-4-3 was reconfirmed by the performance of its parents, *Oryza nivara* and IR24, and its other ancestors, B5580A1-15 and Sigadis (parents of IR127, used to develop IR24), suggesting the lack of genetic sources of resistance.

One accession of Agostano and Balilla and both of Blue Rose and Takao Iku 18 showed a reaction similar to that of the resistant check. It can be inferred that

Colombia 1 carries the resistance genes of Takao Iku 18 because its other parent, Napal, was reported as susceptible when released. Genes of Agostano (and possibly Balilla and Blue Rose) could be responsible for the resistance of Diamante, and ICA10 could be a source of the resistance genes coming from PI215936. Lacrosse's pedigree analysis showed that its ancestors were Colusa, Blue Rose, Shoemed, and Fortuna; the observed resistance could come from the first two varieties. Doing the same exercise with the *Oryzica* varieties, Takao Iku 18 appears to be the most probable source of resistance. For Llanos 4, Taichung 65 and Makalioka might have contributed resistance genes through IRAT122 (Chianan 8/Makalioka).

Pedigree analysis can be used to identify major sources of resistance and to help select parents that enable diverse genes to be incorporated into a breeding program. Pedigree analysis reduces the crosses needed to determine the relationship among the resistance sources identified. ■

Description of rice varieties and lines previously reported to be at least moderately resistant to RHBV, their ancestors, and percentage of plants with RHBV symptoms.

Name	Origin	Designation	Cross	Reaction to RHBV (% of affected plants)
<i>Varieties and lines</i>				
Colombia 1	Colombia	T319E-2M-2M-1M-1M	Napal/Takao Iku 18	3.9
Diamante	Chile	P1-2-2-2-1	Agostano/Blue Rose//Balilla	3.8
ICA10	Colombia	T112D-7P-5T	British Guyana 79/(PI215936 × CI9124)	2.2
INIAP415	Ecuador	P1042-2-3-1B	P738-137-4/P723-40-3-1	28.0
—	IRRI	IR1721-146-4-3	IR24*3/O. <i>nivara</i>	72.9
Lacrosse	USA	Sel. no. 250-121	2913A5-1-3/AL11-1	7.4
Oryzica 1	Colombia	P1429-8-9M-1B	P1223/P1225	23.6
Oryzica Llanos 4	Colombia	P5413-8-3-5-11	CR 1113/IRAT 122//Colombia1/P1274-6-8M	4.4
Oryzica Llanos 5	Colombia	CT5747-24-5-4-2	Colombia 1/P1274-6-8M*2//P2060F4-25-2	0.8
<i>Parents</i>				
Agostano	Italy	Acc. 3135	—	0.7
Agostano	Hungary	Acc. 9334	—	61.7
Balilla	Italy	Acc. 3098	—	88.3
Balilla	Italy	Acc. 3107	—	6.4
Blue Rose	USA	Acc. 1731	—	8.3
Blue Rose	USA	Acc. 1732	—	0.9
IR24	Philippines	IR661-1-140-3	IR8/IR127-2-2	78.5
<i>Oryza nivara</i>	India	Acc. 101508	—	97.9
PI215936	China	Acc. 146	—	3.7
PI215936/CI9214	USA	Acc. 11394	—	6.1
Takao Iku 18	China	Acc. 3037	—	5.7
Takao Iku 18	China	Acc. 6923	—	6.6
<i>Other ancestors</i>				
B5580AL-1-15 (CP-SLO)	USA	Acc. 6993	Century Patna/SLO 17	83.3
Chianan 8	China	Acc. 90	Taichung 65//Mitsui/Oloan-chu	19.8
Colusa	USA	Acc. 1714	—	3.3
Fortuna	USA	Acc. 1708	—	62.5
Makaloka	Madagascar	—	—	13.0
Sigadis	Indonesia	Acc. 5324	Bluebonnet/Benong	75.6
Taichung 65	China	Acc. 79	Shinriki/Kameji	2.0
<i>Checks</i>				
Colombia 1 (resistant)	Colombia	T319E-2M-2M-1M-1M	Napal/Takao Iku 18	5.0
Bluebonnet 50 (susceptible)	USA	—	Rexoro/Fortuna	83.6

Detection of rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) in asymptomatic leaves of tungro-infected rice plants by polymerase chain reaction (PCR)

S. R. Venkitesh, R. W. Briddon, and P. G. Markham, Virus Research Department, John Innes Institute, John Innes Centre for Plant Science Research, Colney Lane, Norwich NR4 7UH, United Kingdom

We have detected the presence of RTBV and rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV) in infected TN1 rice plants by antibody fragment F(ab')₂ enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) 1 wk after

inoculation. Green leafhoppers *Nephotettix virescens* (Distant) were given an acquisition access period of 72 h on plants infected with both rice tungro disease (RTD) viruses and a transmission access period of 24 h on 2-wk-old rice seedlings (2 d-leaf stage). Infected plants were grouped, following F(ab')₂ ELISA tests, for the presence of RTSV (S) or RTBV (B) alone or RTD (B+S) in the newly emerged leaf. RTD-infected rice seedlings were dissected 1 wk after inoculation (3 d-leaf stage) into individual leaves, stem apex, and roots. Each part was then tested for the presence of RTSV or RTBV by F(ab')₂ ELISA and for the presence of RTBV DNA by PCR.

The presence of viral coat proteins varied in different plant parts (Fig. 1). One wk after inoculation, detectable amounts of RTSV and RTBV viral coat proteins were found in the newly emerged leaf (leaf 3), stem apex, and roots.

Among the symptomless leaves (those which emerged before the insect inoculation), very few (3 out of 20) contained detectable amounts of RTSV coat proteins. Neither virus was detectable by F(ab')₂ ELISA in most of them. Two plants showing a typical pattern of virus distribution by F(ab')₂ ELISA (Fig. 1c) were dissected and tested by PCR (Fig. 1d). PCR showed the presence of RTBV DNA in symptomless leaves of these plants.